

EEMverter Manual, version 2.1

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EEMverter philosophy and architecture

EEMverter runs forward responses and inversions of Electrical and ElectroMagnetic (EEM) data and has been born with the intention of handling natively joint inversion of different data types, time-lapse inversion, induced polarization and all dimensionalities (1D,2D & 3D) in the forward response.

Several features are implemented in EEMverter for reaching this purpose, i.e.:

- Definition of distinct meshes for model parameter definition (the model mesh(es), ModMesh), forward computation (the forward mesh(es), ForMesh) and constraint definition (the constraint mesh(es), ConMesh). The model parameters are defined on the nodes of the model mesh(es) and migrated to the forward mesh(es) through (selectable) interpolation(s), and constraints are defined between nodes of mesh(es) and as priors. All ModMesh, ForMesh and ConMesh mesh(es) are defined in vtk format, for being easily visualizable in Paraview (<https://www.paraview.org/>).
- Parametric definition of electrical properties, such that the (complex) electrical conductivity (and, possibly, permittivity and susceptibility) is computed through functions, also integrating petrophysical relations. Examples are the direct inversion of galvanic time-domain induced polarization data in terms of hydraulic conductivity, and the inversion of time-lapse data with direct modelling of temperature.
- Flexible definition of the inversion objective function, such as the data misfit, roughness misfit & prior misfit can be computed with the use of different norms, such as L1, L2, generalized Minimum (Gradient) Support. Distinct norms of distinct types can be assigned to data sets, roughness and prior constraints, and all norm misfits are monitorable through their identifier throughout the entire inversion process.
- Iterative inversion splittable in several inversion cycles. In each cycle it is possible to define: the models inverted in the cycle (for time-lapse inversion); the parameters inverted in the cycles; the constraints used; the data used, and the corresponding norms in the data misfit; the type of forward/Jacobian computation, e.g. 1D or 2D/3D; (some) inversion settings, for instance parameter ranges.

EEMverter is a command-line software for high-performance computing, without any in-built GUI. Nevertheless, an open-source freeware processing GUI for EEMverter is provided, i.e. EEMstudio (developed in Python).

EEMverter is a live project continuously under development, and some features are still under testing and/or implementation and are not released yet for use outside of the EEM Team. Three distinct versions of EEMverter exist:

- LITE version, handling:
 - 2D Modelling of galvanic data with full-decay time-domain IP
 - Single-sounding 1D EM modelling and inversion
 - Multi-sounding modelling (with 1D forward/Jacobian) and inversion of ground-based EM data in continuous acquisition, such as
 - Loupe data
 - tTEM and FloaTEM data

- sTEM profiler data
 - Tem2Go data
 - Limitations are applied to the maximum measured time (1 ms) and maximum inverted resistivity (500 Ohmm)
- Time-lapse inversion
- Synthetic modelling of E&EM data
- PLUS version, licensed for research & commercial purposes, offering in addition to the LITE version
 - Multi-electrode (>2) current injections in galvanic data
 - Handling of Tx and Rx pitch/roll in EM data
 - Joint inversion of E & Ground-EM data
 - Ground EM-IP modelling
 - 2D & 3D Ground EM & Ground EM-IP modelling
 - Automatic data processing
 - Advanced model types (Debye/Warburg, Hydraulic Conductivity, Temperature)
 - Cross gradient-like constraints among IP parameters
 - Geologically constrained inversion
 - Ground Mag & Grav modelling and with external forward/Jacobian kernels
- PRO version, exclusive to The EEM Team (<https://www.the-eem-team.it/>) and to Emergo (<https://www.em-ergo.it/>) for consultancy and professional use, offering full support of Airborne EM data, in 1D, 2D and 3D, also with IP modelling:
 - Pro-features are available for Universities, Research Institutions & Geological Services within negotiable ad-hoc agreements.

All three versions of EEMverter share the same input and output structure: this means that the user is exposed to all the complexity needed for handling joint inversion, time-lapse inversion, 1D/2D/3D forward dimensionality, but not necessarily with access to all these features. For the users of LITE version interested only in basic functionalities this might come as a nuisance, but the possibility to run the inversions in simplified mode allows for a workflow that shields the user from most of the complexities.

Coordinate system and units

EEMverter handles input and output data/models that are intrinsically related to positions on the Earth. Data positions, e.g. EM sounding and electrode positions, as well as models, are referred to a Right-Hand-Side (RHS) cartesian coordinate X-Y-Z system with Z positive upward, positive X pointing toward East and positive Y pointing toward North. For specific data, such as EM data, receiver and transmitter pitch, roll and yaw can be specified. Indicating with small caps the coordinate system in the (moving) EM platform, the attitude is specified with z'-y'-x'' yaw-pitch-roll Tait-Bryan angles (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Euler_angles): positive yaw means counterclockwise rotation along the (upward) Z axis measuring from the X axis; positive pitch means counterclockwise rotation along the y' axis of the moving platform, i.e. nosediving platform, with zero pitch meaning horizontal platform; positive roll means counterclockwise rotation along the x'' axis with the right side of the platform moving down and the left side of the platform moving up;

Pitch-yaw angles with Z-downward definition can be handled with an input .cfg setting that switches the attitude angles at input: FlipYawAndPitch=1 takes as input in the data file positive pitch for a nose-rising platform and positive yaw for a counterclockwise rotation along a Z downward axis and flips the values within EEMverter.

Contrary to geometrical positions, the versus for B and dB/dt sign follows the classic convention of Z-downward positive values.

Position units are expressed in meters and angles in degrees. Data/parameter units are described in the data-specific paragraph

I/O

EEMverter runs in a command window in two different modes, native and simplified:

- in native mode the main input is the .EEM file, which offers all the functionalities of EEMverter, but is complex, because it defines explicitly all the relations among model meshes, forward meshes, constraint meshes, norms in the objective functions, parameter ranges, inversion cycles etc. etc..
- in simplified mode the main input is the data file, and the .EEM file is built internally, with all its dependencies.

In both modes, native and simplified, a configuration (.cfg) file specifies the settings for running EEMverter (when the .cfg file is not present in the call, default values are used).

The output files are:

- the .M33 file, containing the inversion misfit (iteration by iteration and cycle by cycle), the inversion settings and the inversion log;
- the inversion model mesh ModMesh, and, optionally, forward/constraint meshes and misfit/extrapar meshes, in .vtk format;
- the forward data, with format identical to the input data files but different file extensions.

Contrary to other inversion software, EEMverter allows for the automatic internal generation of all the meshes used in the inversion process, to minimize the efforts in setting inversions up. The default settings for mesh generation handle most of the needs of the users, with forward meshes adapted to model meshes automatically. Details on automatic mesh generation are found in the description of the configuration file.

EEMverter uses an online license system: it must be online for running and offline usage is not permitted. PLUS and PRO versions check through the online license system the features enabled by the user's license.

Figure 1 summarizes the I/O structure of EEMverter.

Figure 1. I/O structure of EEMverter.

Inputs

Native (advanced) mode, up to two arguments:

- EEM file name, containing info about model meshes & model/parameter type(s), forward dimensionality and meshes, constraint meshes, inversion cycles, iteration number(s), norms in the objective function, parameter ranges, data lin/log settings, interpolation between model and forward meshes, stopping criterion, data rejection among cycles etc.. The output .M33 file can be used instead of the .EEM file as well, for instance for re-starting an inversion from the last iteration of another one.
- .cfg configuration file name, containing the inversion settings.

Call examples:

- `.\EEMverterLITE_V7.10.exe GradM_fwr_2D_MPA_TwoBlocks.EEM inv_2_2D.cfg`
Using an explicit configuration file
- `.\EEMverterLITE_V7.10.exe GradM_fwr_2D_MPA_TwoBlocks.EEM`
Using default configuration settings

The EEM file contains the names of the model, forward and constraint meshes. These names can be the name of actual meshes, in .vtk format, containing all info, or the names of .cfg files, which allow EEMverter to build these meshes internally. The names of the .cfg files in the EEM file can be different from the name

of the .cfg file in the argument list of the call: a distinct .cfg file can be used for each model/forward/constraint mesh as well.

Simplified mode, up to four arguments:

- Single Data file name (e.g. .qui file for galvanic data or .emy file for inductive data; for detailed extensions and explanation see section “data files”) or Data file List (which contains multiple files to be modelled jointly, .dls extension)
- Configuration file name (extension .cfg), **optional** (*but recommended, because default .cfg values do not handle all types of inversions*)
- Model type number/keyword, **optional**, present only if the configuration setting “ModelType” is defined “external” in the .cfg file
- File name of the table containing the starting model, **optional**, present only if the configuration setting “ModelTypeOfInitialValues” is defined “external” in the .cfg file, extension .txt (simplified table) or .tbl (advanced table)

Call examples:

- `.\EEMverterLITE_V7.10.exe GradM.qua fwr_2_2D.cfg MPA TwoBlocks.txt`
For running a time-domain IP forward response (settings in `fwr_2_2D.cfg`) on a galvanic sequence (`GradM.qua`) with Maximum Phase Angle (MPA) Cole-Cole modelling, with a model defined with two conductive/resistive chargeable blocks in a homogeneous medium (`TwoBlocks.txt`).
- `.\EEMverterLITE_V7.10.exe GradM_IP.quo inv_2_2D.cfg CPA`
For running an inversion (settings in `inv_2_2D.cfg`) on TDIP galvanic synthetic data (`GradM_IP.quo`) with Constant Phase Angle (CPA) modelling.
- `.\EEMverterLITE_V7.10.exe ArnOLD_proc.qui`
For running resistivity-only inversion with default settings on the field data contained in the file `ArnOLD_proc.qui`
- `.\EEMverterLITE_V7.10.exe help`
Default configuration file and list of implemented model types are written

EEM file

EEM file name, containing info about model meshes & model/parameter type(s), forward dimensionality and meshes, constraint meshes, inversion cycles, iteration number(s), norms in the objective function, parameter ranges, data lin/log settings, interpolation between model and forward meshes, stopping criterion, data rejection among cycles etc..

It is subdivided into different sections, i.e.:

- %0, version number
- %1, counters, such as number of Models, ModelMeshes, ForwardGroups, ForwardMeshes, ConstraintMeshes, Norms, Interpolations, Ranges, ClippingAreas, StoppingCriteria, DataGroups, inversion Cycles
- %2 Model section, where the models to be inverted for (or sed for forward modelling) are defined, for instance in terms of model type (which determines the number of parameters and

parameter types), number of models (for instance, in time-lapse inversion, one model for each acquisition time), number of model meshes per model (the parameters are defined on the model meshes, but each parameter of the model type can be defined, in theory, on an independent mesh). Nodes of the Model Mesh(es) have assigned a Region ID, which allows for defining different parameter ranges in the regions and to break automatically constraints among different regions. For each Model Mesh an external file is indicated with the mesh info, either in .vtk format, with explicit definition of the mesh, either in .cfg format, with settings for building the mesh internally in EEMverter.

- %3 Model mesh section, in which the type of mesh is specified (structured/unstructured), and which parameters are defined on the mesh and with what ranges.
- %4 Forward Group section, which is a bundle of several forward meshes connected to the same Data Group. Each forward mesh may contain more than one mesh, actually (for instance one for each sounding in inductive computations), and all meshes of the forward group account for all data in the Data Group.
- %5 Forward Mesh section, with dimensionality definition and “searching radius”, a feature needed for 1D computation for defining how far from a 1D sounding the model mesh is defined. For each Forward Mesh an external file is indicated with the mesh info, either in .vtk format (.vtk format for forward meshes is allowed only for 1D forward meshes), with explicit definition of the mesh, either in .cfg format, with settings for building the mesh internally in EEMverter.
- %6 Constraint Mesh section, where we define the Model Mesh to which the Constraint Mesh is connected and the mesh file name. This name is defined for each Constraint Mesh, and indicates the external file with the mesh info, either in .vtk format, with explicit definition of the mesh, either in .cfg format, with settings for building the mesh internally in EEMverter.
- %7 Norm section, with Norm IDs, types and labels. Which norm is used for constraints is defined in the Model Mesh (for prior constraints) and Constraint mesh (for roughness and time-lapse constraints). Which norm is used for data is defined in the cycle information (the data norm can change among cycles).
- %8 Interpolation section, which defines the interpolation types. The interpolation is set for each Forward Mesh in the Forward Mesh section. If the parameters of the forward Mesh are defined on more than one Model Mesh, a distinct interpolation ID has to be specified for each Model Mesh.
- %9 Range section, where the parameter ranges of the Model Meshes are defined. “Default” means ranges in the .cfg file in the argument of the call. A range ID has to be specified for each parameter of the Model Mesh in the Model Mesh section (and for each region).
- %10 Clipping areas section, where it is possible to define areas in which to keep or discard data. These areas are actually defined in subareas: for each subarea a polyline is defined (through its nodes, no repetition of first and last node), such that only data inside the subareas (InsideOut=1) or outside the subareas (InsideOut=0) are kept for modelling (InsideOut=-1,-2 and 2 are other options that control what happens when the data are on the edges of the subareas). Alternatively, InsideOut = 3 and 4 keep only data within a certain distance from the polyline (controlled by the configuration setting MaxDistanceFromClippingArea). For galvanic data, the clipping area works on the electrode positions.

- %11 Stopping criteria section, which can work on the relative change in the objective function between consecutive iterations (MisfitChange) or data misfit (DataMisfit). The stopping criterion is defined for each inversion cycle, through its identification number defined in this section.
- %12 Data Group section, where the data type corresponding to the data file is defined (see “Data File Extensions” section for details), the number of Norms for each data file (Two distinct norms can be defined, for instance, for resistivity and IP data for Time-Domain (TD) galvanic data), the Lin/log settings for the data, the clipping area ID to use (0 no clipping) and the number of measurements (-1 computes the number from the file), together with the file name.
- %13 Cycle section, in which the cycle info is defined, i.e.
 - the cycle name (used in the .M33 file in the misfit section and, optionally, in the output file names)
 - if the cycle is active (1-> active, 0-> not active and skipped in the execution)
 - the number of iterations per cycle (-1-> forward response only; 0-> forward and jacobian, with jacobian computation necessary for DOI; any other positive number up to 100 for running inversions)
 - the number of models to invert for (needed for time-lapse inversion) and the model IDS
 - the parameters to invert for in the cycle and their IDs (the others are kept constant in the cycle)
 - the number of constraint meshes and their IDs
 - the number of data groups and their IDs and the corresponding Forward Group IDs/Jacobian Group IDs (one for each data group; distinct Forward/Jacobian groups are allowed, for instance for hybrid 1D/3D inversions or for speeding computations up with coarser Jacobian meshes)
 - the data norms (for each data group, with one/two IDs per group depending on the settings in Data Group Section)
 - the flags for rejecting data (one flag for each norm of each Data Group) and the rejection thresholds (one threshold for each norm of each Data Group) for automatic data rejection at the beginning of the cycle (RejectBadFitData=0 -> no rejection; RejectBadFitData=1 -> rejection)
 - the info for damping initialization (RelnitDamping=1 -> damping maxstep is reinitialized to the .cfg setting at the beginning of each cycle; RelnitDamping=0 -> maxstep continues from the value of the previous cycle)
 - the stopping criterion ID
 - the flags for computing DOI and Analysis (1-> compute; 0-> do not compute), Analysis computation still under development
 - the number of inversion settings to be changed compared to the values of the .cfg file, their names and values (it works only for a few setting values, such as parameter ranges)

Configuration (.cfg) file

The configuration file (optional but recommended) contains EEMverter’s settings. These settings are divided into four groups:

- GeneralSettings, containing the .cfg version number;

- AutoEEMSettings, for building internally the EEM file when running in simplified mode: all these settings are used ONLY when running in simplified model; they are NOT USED AT ALL in native mode;
- InversionSettings, such as number of threads, damping, parameter default ranges, setting for forward accuracy and many others, what mesh to write and when; these settings are read only when contained in the .cfg file used as command argument: this setting group is not used when the .cfg file is used in the .EEM file for defining meshes.
- AutoMeshSettings, for building internally the model, constraint and forward meshes. ONLY THESE SETTINGS are used for BUILDING MESHES when using the .cfg file name in the EEM file.

All the settings contained in the .cfg file are used by EEMverter; any setting not present in the file takes the default value. Call “EEMverterLite_V7.10 help” from a command line to get the complete list of .cfg settings, together with the list of model types.

Explanation of the main .cfg settings is given in the following, setting group by setting group. For all other settings, the .cfg file contains a brief explanation of all setting meaning in the comments written after the default values.

AutoEEMSettings:

- **ModelType.** Model type for the inversion. It can be an acronym or a number, or 'external'; when external, it has to be indicated as third argument in EEMverter call. E.g. 1 -> RES. Look at ListOfImplementedModelTypes.txt, generated running “EEMverterLite_V7.10.exe help” (or any other EEMverter version) from a command line, for a complete list of model types and acronyms.
- **ModelDimensionality.** EEMverter uses different meshes for the definition of the model parameters and for the computation of the forward response(s). The dimensionality of the model mesh and the forward response can then be different. For instance, it is possible to run inversions of inductive data using a 1D forward/Jacobian computation with a 2D model dimensionality, in which case the model mesh is automatically built as a ribbon-like mesh that follows the acquisition lines, with uniform spacing along the lines (controlled by the .cfg setting ModelXNodeSpacing) and log-increasing depths. With inductive data it is also possible to run inversions with 3D model dimensionality and 1D forward/Jacobian computation. In this case, the model mesh has a regular XY spacing (controlled by ModelXNodeSpacing and ModelYNodeSpacing) and log-increasing depths. 2D and 3D model meshes can be linked to 3D forward meshes for inductive computations (but not with EEMverterLite). For galvanic computations both 2D and 3D meshed can be connected to 2D forward/Jacobian computations. Finally, the model dimensionality can be set to 1 for single-sounding EM inversions.
- **SequentialAutoStart.** It enables an AutoStart cycle for inductive data that allows to obtain a good starting model for the main inversion cycle. It works creating a single-layer forward mesh and tight horizontal constraints, in order to reach an almost-homogeneous starting model with the right resistivity range. It does not work for galvanic data, where the average apparent resistivity can be used for starting resistivity value. Allowed values: 1 -> run single-layer inversion in a preliminary cycle for setting up starting values; 0 -> don't.

- **SequentialSharp.** It enables a sharp cycle, with AGMS (Asymmetric Generalized Minimum Support) vertical/horizontal constraints, after the main cycle (that runs with L1 or L2 roughness constraints). The Sharp cycle starts from the main cycle model and runs with different roughness regularization. Allowed values: 1 -> Run sharp inversion after previous cycle; 0 -> don't.
- **LinData.** It determines the linear or logarithmic data space. Linear data space is needed when galvanic IP decays or inductive soundings show negative data (for instance with a sign-changing signal as a function of time). Allowed values: 1 -> Linear data space; 0 -> Log data space
- **StopCriterion.** type of stopping criterion for main cycle. Allowed keywords: DataMisfit and MisfitChange.
- **RelNormChange.** Relative change in norm to stop iterations for main cycle with StopCriterion = MisfitChange.
- **SubsetNormChangeSize.** Relative change in norm to stop iterations on any subset of size SubsetNormChangeSize with StopCriterion = MisfitChange.
- **RelSubsetNormChange.** Relative size of model space where the stop criterion must obey RelSubsetNormChange regardless of RelNormChangeD or RelNormChangewith; used with StopCriterion = MisfitChange.
- **DataMisfitThreshold.** Data misfit threshold for StopCriterion = DataMisfit.
- **CycleNite.** Number of iterations in main and sharp cycles.
- **CalcDOI.** 1 -> Calculate Depth of Investigation (DOI), 0 -> Don't.
- **RoughnessConstraintNormType.** This setting controls the type of norm of the roughness constraints in the main cycle. Allowed keywords: L2,L1. With L1 regularization larger values for constraint values are often necessary to obtain convergence when compared to L2 constraint values.
- **SharpSettings.** Settings for sharp constraints in the sharp cycle. The default norm in the sharp cycle is a rescaled asymmetric generalized minimum support (RGMS), with 4 settings: alpha, p1, p2 and constraint-scaling (Figure 2). Alpha controls the relative weight of data and roughness measures in the objective function: smaller alpha values increase roughness misfit, larger alpha values favor data; decrease alpha to obtain sharper models. p1 and p2 control determines the way in which the focusing depends on alpha and on sigma (the default values are to our experience the better compromise); the constraint scaling is used to scale the vertical/horizontal constraints contained in the AutoMeshSettings section (VertConstr and HorizConstr) to obtain focusing (typically 0.1 works well as long as the constraints value work in the main cycle).

SETTING	MEANING/ EFFECT	OPTIMAL VALUE	VALUE HIGHER THAN OPTIMAL	VALUE LOWER THAN OPTIMAL
 σ values < optimal may produce over-constrained inversions				
 α values < optimal shrink time-lapse changes				
 the focusing depends more on α when p values < optimal				

Figure 2. Tuning settings of the Asymmetric Generalized Minimum Support (AGMS) norm.

InversionSettings:

- **RejectNegativeData.** 1 -> reject negative input data, 0 -> don't.
- **RejectOutOfRangeIP.** 1 -> reject out of range IP data (outside the range [MinIPValue,MaxIPValue]); 0 -> don't.
- **MinIPValue.** Minimum IP value in acceptance range.
- **MaxIPValue.** Maximum IP value in acceptance range.
- **RejectTooFewGatesIP.** 1 -> reject IP data (i.e. entire decay) with too few gates after processing (number of gates < MinNGatesIP); 0 -> don't.
- **MinNGatesIP.** When the number of IP gates after processing is smaller than MinNGatesIP (and RejectTooFewGatesIP=1), the entire IP decays are commented out.
- **RejectGalvanicHighSTDdata.** 1 -> rejection of galvanic data with $STD > GalvanicHighSTDdataThreshold$; 0-> do not reject; 2-> do not use in model update, but use to compute the forward response.
- **GalvanicHighSTDdataThreshold.** Relative STD for rejection of galvanic HighSTDdata.
- **RejectInductiveHighSTDdata.** 1 -> rejection of inductive data with $STD > InductiveHighSTDdataThreshold$; 0-> do not reject; 2-> do not use in model update, but use to compute the forward response.
- **InductiveHighSTDdataThreshold.** Relative STD for rejection of inductive HighSTDdata.
- **RecomputeGalvanicSTDs.** 1 -> recompute galvanic data STDs based on signal level (as a function of settings GalvanicNoiseLevel, GalvanicUniformStdDC, GalvanicUniformStdIP,

GalvanicSumSquaredNoise, GalvanicFirstNegStd, GalvanicNCloseGates, GalvanicNCloseFactor, GalvanicCorrelatedNoise); 0 -> keep input STDs; 2 -> add only increased STDs on changing-sign data.

- **GalvanicNoiseLevel.** Voltage noise level for a 10 ms integration time, mV.
- **GalvanicUniformStdDC.** Uniform relative DC STD, galvanic data.
- **GalvanicUniformStdIP.** Uniform relative IP STD, galvanic data.
- **GalvanicSumSquaredNoise.** 1 -> Sum squared values of uniform STD and NoiseLevel-dependent STD; 0 -> Sum values linearly.
- **GalvanicFirstNegStd.** Relative STD on the first negative IP datum.
- **GalvanicNCloseGates.** Number of gates to the left and right of the first IP negative datum where to modify the STDs.
- **GalvanicNCloseFactor.** Scaling factor for the modified STDs in the close gates ($\text{std_total}(k+i), \text{std_total}(k+i) + \text{FirstNegStd} / \text{NCloseFactor}^i$, for $i, 1: \text{NCloseGates}$ and k being the index of the first negative).
- **GalvanicCorrelatedNoise.** Setting controlling the computation of the STD on integral chargeability. 0 -> 0 the total STD for integral chargeability inversion is computed as the RMS of the gates STDs, weighted with the gate width; -> 1 the gate STDs are summed linearly (correlated noise).
- **RecomputeInductiveSTDs.** 1 -> recompute inductive data STDs based on signal level (as a function of settings InductiveNoiseLevel, InductiveUniformStd, InductiveSquaredNoise, InductiveFirstNegStd, InductiveNCloseGates, InductiveNCloseFactor); 0 -> keep input STDs; 2 -> add only increased STDs on changing-sign data.
- **InductiveNoiseLevel.** Noise level at 1 ms, V/m².
- **InductiveUniformStd.** Uniform relative STD, inductive data.
- **InductiveSumSquaredNoise.** 1 -> Sum squared values of uniform STD and NoiseLevel-dependent STD; 0 -> Sum values linearly.
- **InductiveFirstNegStd.** Relative STD on the first inductive negative datum.
- **InductiveNCloseGates.** Number of gates to the left and right of the first negative datum where to modify the STDs.
- **InductiveNCloseFactor.** Scaling factor for the modified STDs in the close gates ($\text{std_total}(k+i), \text{std_total}(k+i) + \text{FirstNegStd} / \text{NCloseFactor}^i$, for $i, 1: \text{NCloseGates}$ and k being the index of the first negative).
- **AddNoise.** This setting is used to add noise to forward data. It works only when the input files have an extension of forward data (.quo for galvanic data and .ely for inductive data) or data sequence (.qua for galvanic data and .evy for inductive data). When adding noise to forward data, the files extension of the output files changes: it becomes .tip for galvanic data and .lil for inductive data. Allowed values: 1 -> add noise to forward files; 0 -> no noise; >1 and <999, add noise, fixed seed (the AddNoise value).
- **WriteAddedNoise.** This setting allows to write the added noise in extra columns of the output files. In this case the file extension becomes .tap for galvanic data and .tin for inductive data. Allowed values: 1 -> write explicitly the added noise in extra columns; 0 -> do not write.

- **NThreads.** This setting controls the parallelization in the forward and Jacobian computations. Not all forward/Jacobian algorithms are parallelized in EEMverter. For galvanic computations, the main parallelization runs for IP computations, with the solution of Poisson's equation executed in parallel over different frequencies, as well as in the time-transform of forward/Jacobian, executed in parallel over different multipoles. For inductive computations, both in 1D and 3D, the parallelization is carried out over frequencies, both for forward and Jacobian. Do not exceed the number of threads present in your CPU. A negative number for this setting allows to use (MaxNThreads-NThreads) threads, where MaxNThreads represents the maximum number of threads of the system (or the number recognized by EEMverter).
- **NThreadsLow.** This setting controls the parallelization in the model update computations, where usually the memory bandwidth does not allow to use all the available threads in a scalable way. Typically, numbers above 10 give a worsening of the computation speed.
- **DOICAAHigh.** High CAA (Cumulated Approximate Analysis) threshold for DOI calculations (Shallow). A factor of 2.0 means that anything below the DOI is as a whole within a factor of 2.0 from the inverted values.
- **DOICAALow.** Low CAA (Cumulated Approximate Analysis) threshold for DOI calculations (Deep). A factor of 5.0 means that anything below the DOI is as a whole within a factor of 2.0 from the inverted values.
- **MinRes, MaxRes, MinM0, MaxM0, MinPhi, MaxPhi, MinTau, MaxTau, MinC, MaxC.** Minimum and Maximum allowed values for parameters resistivity, m0, Phi, tau and C.

AutoMeshSettings:

- **DemFileName.** This setting is used for using an external Digital Elevation Model (DEM) file for computing topography. It works only when UseQuiTopo=0 (for galvanic data) or UseEmyTopo=0 (for inductive data). Allowed DEM file formats: .grd ascii/binary surfer format or .asc ESRI ascii format. Allowed values:
'unique' -> it uses the (first found) .grd/.asc file in the .EEM (or data with auto EEM) input file folder, if present; 'auto' -> same name of the .EEM file (with .grd or .asc extension, not used if non existing); 'none' -> no topography; any other character string ending with back slash \ -> folder name containing multiple .grd/.asc files, in which case it uses the DEM with higher resolution that contains the data.
- **ModelMinDepth.** Minimum depth of the model mesh. A value of -1 means automatic computation of minimum depth. For galvanic data, the automatic minimum depth is equal to the minimum pseudodepth of the data sequence multiplied by MinDepthFactor. For inductive data, the minimum depth is computed as a function of the transmitter area as:
 - area $\leq 5 \text{ m}^2$, ModelMinDepth = 0.5 m;
 - area $\leq 20 \text{ m}^2$, ModelMinDepth = 1 m;
 - area $> 20 \text{ m}^2$, ModelMinDepth = 5 m.
- **ModelMaxDepth.** Maximum depth of the model mesh. A value of -1 means automatic computation of maximum depth. For galvanic data, the automatic maximum depth is equal to the maximum pseudodepth of the data sequence multiplied by MaxDepthFactor. For inductive data, the maximum depth is computed as a function of the transmitter area as:

- area $\leq 5 \text{ m}^2$, ModelMaxDepth = 75 m;
- area $\leq 20 \text{ m}^2$, ModelMaxDepth = 150 m;
- area $> 20 \text{ m}^2$, ModelMaxDepth = 500 m.
- **ModelDefinedDepth.** Optional file name of containing user-defined depths for the model. The file must contain only positive N depths, one per row, with $N = \text{ModelNzNodes} - 1$. Default 'none'. When present, ModelMinDepth and ModelMaxDepth are not used.
- **MinDepthFactor.** Factor for computing automatic minimum depth with galvanic data (minimum depth = minimum pseudodepth*factor).
- **MaxDepthFactor.** Factor for computing automatic maximum depth with galvanic data (maximum depth = maximum pseudodepth*factor).
- **ModelNzNodes.** Number of nodes in the z direction, i.e. number of layers. Given a model minimum and maximum depths, EEMverter computes log-increasing depths with a constant increasing factor between consecutive thicknesses. If the factor becomes smaller than one (i.e. if it is not possible to set constant or increasing thicknesses given the minimum and maximum depths and the number of layers), EEMverter gives an error.
- **ModelXNodeSpacing.** Node spacing in 2D (along the acquisition lines) or 3D (in the x direction) model meshes. A value of -1 means automatic computation of the node spacing. For galvanic data, the mesh nodes are set at the electrode positions. For inductive data, the automatic node spacing depends on the transmitter area as:
 - area $\leq 5 \text{ m}^2$, ModelXNodeSpacing = 5 m;
 - area $\leq 20 \text{ m}^2$, ModelXNodeSpacing = 10 m;
 - area $> 20 \text{ m}^2$, ModelXNodeSpacing = 40 m.
- **ModelYNodeSpacing.** Node spacing in 3D (in the y direction) model meshes. A value of -1 means automatic computation of the node spacing, depending on the transmitter area as:
 - area $\leq 5 \text{ m}^2$, ModelYNodeSpacing = 5 m;
 - area $\leq 20 \text{ m}^2$, ModelYNodeSpacing = 10 m;
 - area $> 20 \text{ m}^2$, ModelYNodeSpacing = 40 m.
- **UseAppRhoForInitialValue.** 1-> Use average galvanic apparent resistivity as starting value for resistivity/conductivity parameters, instead of ModelInitialValues (when galvanic data are present); 0-> use ModelInitialValues. Do not use UseAppRhoForInitialValue = 1 for forward computations.
- **ModelTypeOfInitialValues.** keyword identifying the type of starting/prior values (the values are specified by the ModelInitialValues/ModelPriorValues settings for keywords ModelType, ModelMesh, autoMPA, autoMIC, autoBIC, autoRCC, autoCCC, autoWHYCDF). Allowed keywords:
 - ModelType (all values of the model type defined in the EEM file);
 - ModelMesh (all values of the model mesh defined in the EEM file);
 - external (fourth argument in EEMverter call, for external .txt/.tbl/.srf look-up table/MultiSurface model);
 - autoMPA (Rho0,PhiMax,TauPhi,C); In this case the four parameters of the Maximum Phase Angle (MPA) re-parameterization of the Cole-Cole model are listed by the ModelInitialValues/ModelPriorValues settings. These values are used for computing the starting/prior value of the modelling for any ModelType of the inversion. For instance, if

ModelType=RCC is set in the AutoEEMSettings, the MPA starting/prior values are transformed by EEMverter into the corresponding RCC (Resistivity Cole-Cole model) parameters. In this way it is possible to start inversions with any Cole-Cole reparameterization from the same starting model without changing the configuration file. For CPA modelling, the maximum phase of any Cole-Cole re-parameterization is used as starting value for the phase of the CPA model.

- autoMIC (Sigma0,Sigma2ndMax,TauSigma,C), for Maximum Imaginary Conductivity re-parameterization of the Cole-Cole model;
- autoBIC (SigmaBulk,Sigma2ndMax,TauSigma,C) for Bulk and Imaginary Conductivity re-parameterization of the Cole-Cole model;
- autoRCC (Rho0,M0,TauRho,C) for classic resistivity Cole-Cole model;
- autoCCC (Sigma0,M0,TauSigma,C) for classic conductivity Cole-Cole model;
- autoWHYCDF (SigmaW,HydrCond,Dplus,C,FormFactor) for Water and Hydraulic Conductivity, Diffusion coefficient in the Stern layer, frequency exponent C and formation factor F;
- .tbl file name (text file containing a look-up table for starting values, prior constraints, parameter regions/ranges and scaling-by-region for roughness constraints, advanced format);
- .srf file name (text file containing region definition through delimiting surfaces, together with starting values, parameter ranges, prior constraints and scaling-by-region for roughness constraints);
- .txt file name (text file containing a model look-up table, simplified format).
- **ModelNumberOfInitialValues.** Number of initial values, to be defined accordingly to ModelTypeOfInitialValues (always 4 for autoXXX and 5 for autoWHYCDF).
- **ModelInitialValues.** Starting parameters, one for each ModelNumberOfInitialValues. For instance, with ModelTypeOfInitialValues = autoMPA four numbers should be written: Rho0,PhiMax,TauPhi and C.
- **ModelPriorValues.** Prior parameters, one for each ModelNumberOfInitialValues.
- **ModelPriorConstr.** Prior constraints, one for each ModelNumberOfInitialValues.
- **UseQuiTopo.** 1-> use qui topography (not allowed with 3D meshes); 0-> use topography from DEM file (.grd or .asc).
- **UseEmyTopo.** 1-> use emy topography (not allowed with 3D meshes); 0-> use topography from DEM file (.grd or .asc).
- **RoughnessORTimeLapse.** This setting defines if the .cfg file used for defining a constraint mesh in the .EEM file defines intra-mesh constraints (i.e. vertical or horizontal constraints within a model mesh) or cross-meshes constraints (i.e. time-lapse or cross-mesh constraints). 0 -> Roughness constraint mesh; 1 -> Time-lapse/Cross-mesh constraint between distinct meshes: from each node of the corresponding model mesh to the closest node (within RefCrossLineDistance) of the mesh identified by ReferenceModelMeshID; 2 -> Roughness constraint between distinct lines of the same 2D mesh (for inductive models, not for galvanic models): from each node of each line to the closest node of any line within searching distance RefTLXDistance; 3 -> Cross-gradient-like constraint mesh.

- **MaxTLXDistance.** Maximum distance among nodes for setting Time-lapse/Cross-mesh/cross-line constraints (RoughnessORTimeLapse \geq 1).
- **RefTLXDistance.** Reference distance for scaling the Time-lapse/Cross-mesh/cross-line constraints. Constraint $STD = \max(\text{InputSTD}, \text{InputSTD} * \text{Dist} / \text{RefTLXDistance})$, Dist being the closest node distance.
- **ElevRefHorizConstr.** 1 -> Elevation-referenced horizontal constraints; 0 -> Depth-referenced horizontal constraints (RoughnessORTimeLapse=0).
- **VertConstr.** Vertical constraint values (relative values), one for each ModelNumberOfInitialValues (RoughnessORTimeLapse=0). A vertical constraint equal to 1.0 gives a misfit = 1.0 in the objective function when the difference between constrained parameters is within a factor of 1.0 (.i.e. 100% variation).
- **HorizConstrX.** X horizontal constraint values (relative values), one for each ModelNumberOfInitialValues (RoughnessORTimeLapse=0), for constraints in 2D model meshes or for constraints in the X direction in 3D model meshes.
- **HorizConstrY.** Y horizontal constraint values (relative values), one for each ModelNumberOfInitialValues (RoughnessORTimeLapse=0).
- **TLXReferenceModelMeshID.** Time-lapse/cross-mesh reference model mesh ID. The constraints are among the model mesh indicated in the EEM file and the model mesh indicated in the .cfg file through TLXReferenceModelMeshID.
- **TLXConstr.** Time-lapse/Cross-mesh/Cross-line constraint values, one for each ModelNumberOfInitialValues (RoughnessORTimeLapse=1)

ModMesh, ForMesh, ConMesh files

Explicit meshes in .vtk format can be pointed at in the .EEM file for running inversions. This allows to use, for instance, the model of another inversion as ModMesh. Only 1D Forward meshes in .vtk format are allowed: 2D and 3D forward meshes need to be built internally starting from a .cfg file.

Outputs

.M33 file

It contains five parts and can be used as input as well, instead of the EEM file. In this case, as long as the model meshes have been written during inversion (it depends on the .cfg settings on output writing), the inversion re-starts from the last written iteration of the last active cycle. The five parts of the M33 file are:

- IterationMisfit, where the data/prior/roughness/total misfit is shown iteration by iteration, cycle by cycle, but also norm by norm
- ExtendedEEM, where the EEM info is present, with extra columns with counters about, for instance: number of data; number of nodes/cells in meshes; data rejection rate, when applied. This part is used when the .M33 file is used as input
- All the .cfg settings used in the computations
- The inversion log
- The total runtime, and how it is spent

ModMesh .vtk file(s)

It contains the model parameters for forward/inversion computations, the Depth Of Investigation (DOI) estimate and many other info. Always written. Several values are defined in each node of the mesh (POINT-TYPE field vtk format): the meaning of the columns in the point-type field is explained at the end of the file. The DOI info has the following meaning (when computed): 0-> node above DOI; 1-> node below conservative DOI, above deep DOI; 2-> node below DOI. The DOI info is different parameter by parameter. For cutting model areas below DOI, use the “extract component” Paraview filter on the DOI column (column 7, 6 in Paraview that counts columns from 0) and make a threshold on the DOI value (e.g. $0 < DOI < 2$ or $DOI = 0$). The “extract component” step is not necessary with newer Paraview versions (e.g. above 5.12).

ForMesh .vtk file(s)

It contains the forward mesh and the corresponding parameters. Optionally written. The parameters in the forward mesh(es) are obtained interpolating the model parameters into the forward mesh cells. The interpolation function is defined in the .EEM file when running in native mode, or in the .cfg file when running in simplified mode (but the .cfg settings in simplified mode do not control all interpolation features, which depend also on the cycles activated by the settings and by the model type). This mesh is the one visualized by EEMstudio in the Processing/Visualization window.

ForMesh misfit .vtk file(s)

It contains the data misfit visualizable in 3D space. Optionally written. For galvanic data, the misfit file contains DC/IP data/misfit/STDs pseudosections. For inductive data, a Gate-by-Gate .vtk misfit file is written as well, with gate misfit visualized with depth increasing with time (for multi-moment datasets, higher moments are visualized at higher depths). Misfit files are used and visualized in EEMstudio.

ForMesh ExtraPar .vtk file(s)

It contains extra info, such as the electrode position (for galvanic data) or the sounding elevation (for inductive data). Optionally written.

ConMesh .vtk file(s)

It contains the connectivity of the vertical/horizontal constraints, as well as constraint strength and (as output) the constraint misfit. Optionally written.

Data files

File extensions

Differently from all other EEMverter input files, the file extensions of input E&EM data are case sensitive: small caps are used for time-domain data, while capital caps are used for frequency-domain data. All the frequency-domain data files and corresponding computations are still under development.

Table 1. File extension of EEMverter data files.

File description	Extension	Italian Disney name	English Disney name	Picture	Hat/hair ribbon Color	Data Type
Galvanic input file, data measured in the field	.qui – TD .QUI – FD	Qui	Huey		Red	2 (res & TD full-decay IP) 21 (res & TD Int IP) 22 (res only) 4 FD IP
Galvanic input file, forward data without noise (the noise can be added in EEMverter to data in .quo files also when running inversions)	.quo – TD .QUO – FD	Quo	Dewey		Blue	2 (res & TD full-decay IP) 21 (res & TD Int IP) 22 (res only) 4 FD IP
Galvanic input file, acquisition sequence (no data included)	.qua – TD .QUA – FD	Qua	Louie		Green	2 (res & TD full-decay IP) 21 (res & TD Int IP) 22 (res only) 4 FD IP
Galvanic input file, forward data with noise	.tip – TD .TIP – FD	Tip	Morty		Red	2 (res & TD full-decay IP) 21 (res & TD Int IP) 22 (res only) 4 FD IP
Galvanic input file, forward data with noise and noise values contained in extra columns	.tap – TD .TAP – FD	Tap	Ferdie		Blue	2 (res & TD full-decay IP) 21 (res & TD Int IP) 22 (res only) 4 FD IP
Inductive input file, data measured in the field	.emy – TD .EMY – FD	Emy	April		Yellow	1 TD EM 3 FD EM

Inductive input file, forward data without noise (the noise can be added in EEMverter to data in .ely files also when running inversions)	.ely – TD .ELY – FD	Ely	May		Blue	1 TD EM 3 FD EM
Inductive input file, acquisition sequence (no data included)	.evy – TD .EVY – FD	Evy	June		Green	1 TD EM 3 FD EM
Inductive input file, forward data with noise	.lil – TD .LIL – FD	Lily	Millie		Green	1 TD EM 3 FD EM
Inductive input file, forward data with noise and noise values contained in extra columns	.tin – TD .TIN – FD	Tiny	Melody		Purple	1 TD EM 3 FD EM
External not-native input file, measured data, column based	.odd					0
External not-native input file, forward response, column based	.bbo					0
Borehole input file, measured data	.bHl					5
Borehole input file, forward data	.lHd					5

Data List file .dls

For running inversions in simplified mode with multiple data files, for instance in time-lapse or joint inversions, the data list file (extension .dls) can be used. Inside the data list file, several input data files can be listed, line by line, specifying in each line four things: 1) data file name; 2) datatype (see table 1 for details); 3) the ID of the clipping area (where to keep or discard data, with info contained in the .cfg file); 4) the model id, to specify if we are running a time-lapse inversion with multiple models linked through time-lapse constraints or a join inversion where several datasets point to the same model ID.

For example, a .dls file for resistivity Time-Lapse or Cross-Mesh inversion looks like:

% FileName	DataType	ClipAreaID	ModelID
File1.qui	22	0	1
File2.qui	22	0	2
File3.qui	22	0	3

The .dls file is the standard input for EEMverter generated by EEMstudio and must be present in the folder that contains the inversion results for loading the results in EEMstudio. For this reason, it is possible to generate automatically the .dls file with EEMverter when running an inversion in simplified mode using a single data file as first argument (and not the .dls file), using the .cfg setting WriteDlsFile=1.

Galvanic time-domain data format: .qui/.quo/.qua/.tip/.tap files

The EEMverter file format for time-domain galvanic data has been designed to handle data acquired with most of the instrumentations available, as well as with features not yet supported.

The novelty, when compared to other inversion codes, are:

- Piecewise linear current waveform with non-instantaneous turn-on and turn-off, also with the possibility to indicate quadrupole-by-quadrupole intermediate current values.
- Multipoles (instead of simple quadrupoles), with multiple current injections and, possibly, with different current waveforms for each current injection.
- Multiple IP decays for the same multipole (for instance for handling a fast decay obtained with high base frequency and high stack number and a slow decay with low base frequency and small stack number).
- 50% and 100% duty cycle with explicit definition of the stacking procedure.
- New definition of integral chargeability, which is defined as the weighted average of the gate values, the weight being the gate widths; commented out data are not used in the computation of integral chargeability.
- Definition of electrode positions along lines, which allows to define the induction along cables.
- Explicit definition of processing flags for DC and IP data, which allow to comment data out in the inversion procedures, but keeping the data in the file.

The galvanic data files, like the .EEM/.M33 files, are defined in sections:

- %0 comments.
- %1 version number and metadata (metadata are not used in the inversion except for the date in time-lapse inversion modelling thermal diffusion, but they are used in EEMstudio). For general EPSG coordinate system format, CoordRef should be written as EPSG:XXXXX, where XXXXX indicates the EPSG identifier.
- %2 counters for all subsequent sections.
- %3 scaling section, which allows to change electrode spacing with a few modifications (for synthetic modelling without georeferenced coordinates).
- %4 Electrode positions/info.
- %5 Lines that contain electrodes (for commenting out group of data easily and for modelling EM effects).
- %6 Filter info. Each line represents a filter description, with number of frequencies NFreq, and, for each frequency, settings: Frequency, type (0-> Butterworth filter; 1-> Gaussian filter) and order (<1 for gaussian filter).
- %7 Gate info, also with gate type (0-> no gating; 1-> box-car gating; 2-> gaussian gating, not implemented yet). Gate flags allow to comment out gates from the entire dataset. GateTime represents the center gate time, GateWidth the whole gate width. Times written in seconds.
- %8 Stack information (too many stacks cause instability with CPA-like modelling with gate integration). Stack info is described as: Stacksize, (t_i, a_i, i=1,StackSize). For instance, in a 50% duty cycle acquisition, two StackID should be defined, with different stack times:

one StackID for the DC stacking, indicating the starting times of the voltage raising during the on time and one StackID for the IP stacking, indicating the starting times of the voltage drop in the off time (Figure 3a and 3b). On the contrary, with 100% duty cycle, the same stacking times are used for both DC and IP data (Figure 3c).

Figure 3. Examples of stacking times with 50% duty cycle injection for DC data (a) and IP data (b) and with 100% duty cycle injection for both DC and IP data (c).

- %9 Current waveform, defined as piecewise linear current. The current waveform is defined by 3 main settings: NCurrValues, WaveType and NWavePoints. NCurrValues defines the number of current measurements used in the waveform definition, Wavetype is the type of waveform (Wavetype 1-> step response; 2-> user-defined piecewise linear waveform) and NWavePoints indicates the number of time-amplitude points defined in the piecewise linear waveform. Typically, NCurrValues=1 and the current values are not indicated explicitly as values, but as keywords with fractions of the measured current values (the measured current values are indicated in section 11, quadrupole by quadrupole). This case is indicated in Figure 4b, where the amplitude values are indicated as i1#x.y, where x.y indicates the fraction of the measured current i1# (i1# because Figure 4b represent a waveform with only one current measurement, i.e. NCurrValues=1). With NCurrentValues=0, the current values should be indicated explicitly in the waveform (Figure 4a). Finally, in Figure 4c for all the 11 points of the waveform (NWavePoints=11) different current measurements are used (NCurrValues=11): in this case for each quadrupole in section 11 current measurements should be indicated. With WaveType=2 both instantaneous ($t_{i+1}=t_i$) and non-instantaneous ($t_{i+1}>t_i$) turn on and off are allowed. NON-INSTANTANEOUS turn on/off is not compatible with gate integration.

Figure 4. Three possible ways of defining the same current waveform in terms of pairs of time and current amplitude. a) with settings $NCurrValues=0$, $WaveType=2$ and $NWavePoints=11$ and explicit current values indicated as amplitudes; b) with settings $NCurrValues=1$, $WaveType=2$ and $NWavePoints=11$, with current amplitudes indicated as fraction of the measured current $i1\#$; c) with $NCurrValues=11$, $WaveType=2$ and $NWavePoints=11$, with all current amplitudes expressed as measured currents.

- %10 Gateset section, which specifies the decays associated to each multipole and the IP units, through Transtype. Transtype = 0 -> voltages; Transtype = 1 -> 50% duty cycle mV/V; Transtype = 2 -> 100% duty cycle mV/V. A distinct StackID must be indicated for the DC measurements and the IP decay(s), as well as FilterID.
- %11 Data section, one line for each multipole. Multipole because multipole current injections, possibly each with multipole current electrodes, are allowed. Each line contains also the data STDs (which can be re-computed automatically by EEMverter through the .cfg settings) and the processing flags. STDs are stated also for the current measurements. Data are not needed in .qua format. Extra columns with the noise added are present in the .tap format.

Commenting flags are allowed for electrodes, lines, gates, resistivity, integral chargeability and all gates in the IP decays. Allowed values:

- Flag=1 -> data are entirely commented out and not used in the computations
- Flag=2 -> data used in the mesh generation and forward computations, but not used in the model update – **beta features, bugs might be present**

The apparent resistivity and the integral chargeability values are dummy inputs, not used by EEMverter: they are computed internally. The integral chargeability is computed as the weighted average of the gate values, the weight being the gate widths; commented out data are not used in the computation of integral chargeability.

EEMverter reads the data and put them in the data vector differently, depending on the data type:

- DataType=2 -> the entire info in the data set is used, with resistivity and full-decay(s) data going in the inversion
- DataType=21-> only resistivity and integral chargeability go in the inversion: the full-decay(s) IP data are not used nor computed
- DataType=22-> only resistivity goes in the inversion: the IP data are not used nor computed

Inductive time-domain data format: .emy/.ely/.evy/.lil/.tin files

The EEMverter file format for time-domain inductive data has been designed to handle all the ground-based, waterborne and airborne systems available, as well as systems that do not exist yet. We tried to include any possible characteristic of the acquisition systems that should be modelled for an accurate forward response, from the system transfer function to the acquisition geometry.

In particular, system geometry has been a key feature for the definition of the format, with offset systems such as TEMPEST for airborne data and Loupe for ground-based data at the center of the format definition, as well as the need to contain all information for 3D modelling of the data. This means that, instead of indicating the simple relative distance between Tx and Rx, the full coordinates in 3D space are indicated, together with the complete Tx and Rx attitude.

Furthermore, a feature not yet present in current systems has been introduced, i.e. the capability of having multiple transmitters acting at the same time, each with its own position and attitude and possibly composed by more than one coil (e.g. for modelling explicitly the bucking coil or zero-position systems with offset Tx coils). This feature has been introduced having in mind “swarms” of drones and/or backpack-mounted systems, that might allow for unconventional acquisitions.

The positions and attitude of the transmitters are defined by the combination of two types of information:

- The description of the transmitter “platform(s)”, in terms of coil relative positions and shapes (section %9 of the file).
- The position of the center of the transmitter platform(s) and the transmitter attitude, defined sounding by sounding (section %12 of the file); the attitude is specified with z-y'-x'' yaw-pitch-roll Tait-Bryan angles (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Euler_angles).

The actual position of the transmitter, for a given sounding, is computed combining the sounding-specific position of the center of the transmitter (TxX, TxY, TxZ) with the platform-specific relative position of the coil ($SubTxX, SubTxY, SubTxZ$) through the rotation matrix $R(\alpha, \beta, \gamma)$ that depends on the yaw-pitch-roll angles α, β, γ (See also Figure 5):

$$\begin{bmatrix} X \\ Y \\ Z \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} TxX \\ TxY \\ TxZ \end{bmatrix} + R(\alpha, \beta, \gamma) \cdot \begin{bmatrix} SubTxX \\ SubTxY \\ SubTxZ \end{bmatrix}$$

With null attitude angles, the relation simplifies to:

$$\begin{bmatrix} X \\ Y \\ Z \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} TxX \\ TxY \\ TxZ \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} SubTxX \\ SubTxY \\ SubTxZ \end{bmatrix}$$

Similar relations hold for the receiver position, defined by the combination of:

- The description of the receiver “platform(s)”, in terms of coil relative positions and shapes (section %10 of the file).

- The position of the center of the receiver platform and the receiver attitude, defined sounding by sounding (section %12 of the file); also for the receiver, the attitude is specified with z-y'-x'' yaw-pitch-roll Tait–Bryan angles (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Euler_angles).

Similarly to Transmitter definition, the actual position of the receiver, for a given sounding, is computed combining the sounding-specific position of the center of the receiver (RxX, RxY, RxZ) with the platform-specific relative position of the coil ($CoordRxX, CoordRxY, CoordRxZ$) through the rotation matrix $R(\alpha', \beta', \gamma')$ that depends on the yaw-pitch-roll angles α', β', γ' (See also Figure 5):

$$\begin{bmatrix} X \\ Y \\ Z \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} RxX \\ RxY \\ RxZ \end{bmatrix} + R(\alpha', \beta', \gamma') \cdot \begin{bmatrix} CoordRxX \\ CoordRxY \\ CoordRxZ \end{bmatrix}$$

Figure 5. Actual position of Transmitters Tx and Receivers Rx as a combination of sounding-specific positions of the Tx/Rx (red circles) and platform-specific relative distances of the coils ($SubTxX, SubTxY, SubTxZ$). The attitude angles are relative to the sounding-specific positions of the Tx/Rx.

These inductive data files, like the .EEM/.M33 files, are defined in sections:

- %0 comments
- %1 version number and metadata (metadata are not used in the inversion except for the date in time-lapse inversion modelling thermal diffusion, but they are used in EEMstudio). For general EPSG coordinate system format, CoordRef should be written as EPSG:XXXXX, where XXXXX indicates the EPSG identifier. PlotMode handles the sounding position in the visualization. Allowed values:1-> tx position; 2-> rx position; 3-> average tx-rx position.
- %2 counters for all subsequent sections. If the counters do not match the number of lines in the sections, error will occur in the reading.
- %3 Lines with soundings. The line string is dummy in EEMverter. The number of soundings of the lines NSoundings and sounding IDs SoundIDs must match the number of soundings. Lines can be flagged out (LineFlag=1) for removing them from computations.
- %4 Filter info. Each line represents a filter description, with number of frequencies NFreq, and, for each frequency, settings: Frequency, type (0-> butterworth filer; 1-> gaussian filter) and order (<1 for gaussian filter)
- %5 System response information. System response ID, period, stack size, stack amplitudes, number of times, times, amplitudes.
- %6 Gate info, also with gate type (0-> no gating; 1-> box-car gating; 2-> gaussian gating). Gating is still under development for inductive computation. Gate flags allow to comment out gates from the entire dataset. GateTime represents the center gate time, GateWidth the whole gate width. Times written in seconds.
- %7 Stack information. Same meaning of galvanic implementation, but only one stack for inductive data should be modelled.
- %8 Current waveform, defined as piecewise linear current. Same definition of galvanic implementation (look at details in the galvanic file description).
- %9 Transmitter section. A transmitter “platform” might be composed of multiple loops or magnetic dipoles, named SubTx. For each SubTx the following settings are defined: SubTxType, SubTxSettings, NMoments and, for each Moment, MomentCWID (CurrentWaveformID), MomentFlag and MomentNTurns. The SubTx01Settings depend on the SubTxType:
 - With type 1, i.e. magnetic dipole as Tx, the settings are x,y,z of the dipole, polarity and equivalent area;
 - With type 2, i.e. piecewise linear loop, the settings are nvertices, xs, ys, zs, polarity, area (where xs, ys, zs are the positions of the vertices of the loop);
 - With type 3, i.e. circular loop, the settings are x,y,z of the center of the loop, polarity and area.
- % 10 Receiver section. A receiver “platform” might contain several receiver positions NRxCoords (as for instance in the SkyTEm platform, where Z and X receivers are in different frame positions) as well as several receivers NSubRxs. For each receiver SubRx the following settings are defined: SubRxPolarity, SubRxCoordID, SubRxPrimary, SubRxFlag, SubRxType and SubRxSettings. The setting SubRxPrimary controls the amount of primary field to be modelled. For now, no primary is modelled in the forward response (SubRxPrimary=0), regardless of the .emy file setting. The

setting SubRxType defines the type of receiver: SubRxType=1 means coil receiver, with SubRxSettings equal to scaling and nominal area (helpful in defining signal level).

- % 11 Gateset section, which specifies the decays associated to each sounding, their gates, the field type (FieldType=0 -> B field; FieldType=1 -> dB/dt field), the receiver polarity (through DecaySubRxID) and the signal units, through Transtype. Transtype=0 -> V/Am² for dB/dt field and Vs/Am²=T/A for B field, i.e. signal normalized by Tx current and number of turns; Transtype=1 -> V/m² for dB/dt field and Vs/m²=T for B field; Transtype=2 -> V for dB/dt field and V-s for B field, i.e. signal multiplied by receiver nominal area. For each decay of the gateset, the following settings are defined: DecayFlag, DecayMomentIDs (one for each Tx), DecayStackID, DecayFilterID, DecaySysRespIDs (one for each Tx; use zero if system response is not present), DecaySubRxID, DecayNGates and DecayGateIDs.
- % 12 Data section, one line for each sounding. Transmitter position and attitude are specified for all the Transmitters (the number of transmitters is specified in the GateSet identified by the GateSetID). Each line contains also the STDs (which can be re-computed automatically by EEMverter through the .cfg settings) and the processing flags. STDs are stated also for the current measurements and the Tx and Rx positions and attitude angles. Data are not needed in .evy format. Extra columns with the noise added are present in the .tin format.

Commenting flags are allowed for lines, gates, sub-receivers, moments, decays and all gate-by-gate data in the soundings. Allowed values:

- Flag=1 -> data are entirely commented out and not used in the computations
Flag=2 -> data used in the mesh generation and forward computations, but not used in the model update – **beta features, bugs might be present**

Input table and surface files

In order to define non-uniform starting/prior values of the model meshes, it is possible to use an external file table or surface file (through the .cfg setting ModelTypeOfInitialValues). Two types of table files are allowed: a simplified version and an advanced one. Furthermore, a .srf file, which defines the model meshes in terms of regions delimited by surfaces, is available.

Simplified table, .txt extension

The simplified table allows to define the starting/prior values of an inversion by means of a table. The parameter values are defined in terms of a ModelType and are internally converted to the parameter types used in the modelling, similarly to what happens with the autoXXX keyword for ModelTypeOfInitialValues. In the table the values are identified by symbols, which are organized in entries specified with a given order (the table Order can be XZY or XYZ). If the model mesh built with the table has a number of x, y or z nodes larger than the table number of x,y or z entries, the table is automatically extended with la last row/column/layer to fill the entire mesh. Table dimension, in terms of dx, dy, MinDepth and MaxDepth can be optionally defined after the number of x, y , z entries.

Table Example:

ModelType

14

Number of symbols

5

Symbols and parameter values

a 100 10 0.1 0.5

b 100 10 0.1 0.5

c 100 10 0.1 0.5

d 100 10 0.1 0.5

e 100 10 0.1 0.5

Number of x,y,z table entries (optionally, dx,dy,MinDepth,MaxDepth)

2 3 3 (10, 10, 5, 1, 10)

Order

XZY

Table

a a

a a

a a

b b

b b

b b

c c

c c

d e

Advanced table, .tbl extension

The advanced table, when compared to the simplified table, allows to:

- Define different entries for starting and prior values
- Define prior STD and region IDs
- Define constraint scaling-by-region

Surfaces file, .srf extension

The .srf file allows to define the starting/prior/constraint values of the ModMesh and ConMesh by means of regions delimited by surfaces. Used for modelling bathymetry and for Geologically-constrained inversion.

Modelling

Forward modelling and inversion in EEMverter are handled in a similar manner, the main distinction being the number of iterations set in the .EEM file (native mode) or in the .cfg file (simplified mode). In the following guidelines on how to set up forward and inversion modelling are proposed, as well as explanations on the demo files provided with the EEMverter Lite release.

How to run and tune standard inversions

For understanding how to tune inversions in EEMverter, it is necessary to understand how the objective function and the stopping criterion are defined, in terms of data values and uncertainty and inversion parameters and constraints, as well as how to define starting values and model discretization. In the following, all these topics are briefly treated, together with multi-cycle inversions and integral-chargeability/full-decay galvanic inversions.

Model dimensionality and forward dimensionality

The first consideration to be made for understanding inversions in EEMverter is that the model parameters are defined on (the nodes of) model meshes (ModMesh(es)) and the forward computations are carried out in the forward meshes (ForMesh(es)), in which the parameters are defined interpolating the model parameters into the discretization of the forward meshes. For this reason, two dimensionalities are defined:

- The dimensionality of the model meshes, controlled in simplified inversion mode by the .cfg setting ModelDimensionality;
- The dimensionality of the forward meshes, controlled in simplified inversion model by the .cfg settings DimensionalityEM and DimensionalityDCIP.

This means that for inductive data it is possible to run inversions with:

- 2D model meshes and 1D forward meshes (inv_2_1D.cfg configuration file in the EEMstudioLite distribution); in this case the model mesh is automatically built as a ribbon-like mesh that follows the acquisition lines, with uniform spacing along the lines (controlled by the .cfg setting ModelXNodeSpacing) and log-increasing depths;
- 3D model meshes and 1D forward meshes (inv_3_1D.cfg configuration file in the EEMstudioLite distribution); in this case the model mesh has a regular XY spacing (controlled by ModelXNodeSpacing and ModelYNodeSpacing) and log-increasing depths;
- 2D model meshes and 3D forward meshes; in this case the model mesh is automatically built as a ribbon-like mesh that follows the acquisition lines, with uniform spacing along the lines (controlled by the .cfg setting ModelXNodeSpacing) and log-increasing depths, while the forward meshes are built with domain decomposition and octree topology;
- 3D model meshes and 3D forward meshes; in this case the model mesh has a regular XY spacing (controlled by ModelXNodeSpacing and ModelYNodeSpacing) and log-increasing depths, while the forward meshes are built with domain decomposition and octree topology;

Similarly, for galvanic data it is possible to combine:

- 2D model meshes and 2D forward meshes (inv_2_2D.cfg configuration file in the EEMstudioLite distribution); in this case the model mesh is automatically built as a ribbon-like mesh that follows the acquisition lines, with uniform spacing along the lines (at the electrode positions) and log-increasing depths;
- 3D model meshes and 2D forward meshes; in this case the model mesh has a regular XY spacing (controlled by ModelXNodeSpacing and ModelYNodeSpacing) and log-increasing depths, while the forward mesh is built along the acquisition lines.

Objective function and balance between data and regularization

The objective function of EEMverter is a balance between misfit of data, smoothness constraints, time-lapse constraints and prior constraints defined as:

$$\chi = \sqrt{\frac{\Phi_d(\delta \mathbf{d}) + \Phi_R(\delta \mathbf{m}_R) + \Phi_{TL}(\delta \mathbf{m}_{TL}) + \Phi_P(\delta \mathbf{m}_P)}{N_d + N_R + N_{TL} + N_P}} = \sqrt{\frac{N_d \chi_d^2 + N_R \chi_R^2 + N_{TL} \chi_{TL}^2 + N_P \chi_P^2}{N_d + N_R + N_{TL} + N_P}}$$

Where:

- $\Phi_d(\delta \mathbf{d}) = N_d \cdot \chi_d^2$ represents the measure of the data misfit vector $\delta \mathbf{d} = \mathbf{d} - \mathbf{f}$, i.e. the difference between data vector \mathbf{d} and forward response vector \mathbf{f} ; for standard L2 norm, the data misfit reduces to $\chi_d = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N_d} \cdot \sum_{i=1}^{N_d} \left(\frac{d_i - f_i}{\sigma_{d_i}} \right)^2}$, where σ_{d_i} represents the standard deviation of the i^{th} datum.
- $\Phi_R(\delta \mathbf{m}_R) = N_R \cdot \chi_R^2$ represents the measure of the roughness vector $\delta \mathbf{m}_R = -\mathbf{R} \cdot \mathbf{m}$, i.e. the misfit of the intra-model vertical/horizontal constraints; for standard L2 norm, the roughness misfit reduces to $\chi_R = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N_R} \cdot \sum_{i,j} \left(\frac{m_i - m_j}{\sigma_{R_{i,j}}} \right)^2}$, where $\sigma_{R_{i,j}}$ represents the standard deviation of the roughness constraint between the i^{th} and the j^{th} model parameters, .
- $\Phi_{TL}(\delta \mathbf{m}_{TL}) = N_{TL} \cdot \chi_{TL}^2$ represents the measure of the time-lapse roughness vector $\delta \mathbf{m}_{TL} = -\mathbf{R}_{TL} \cdot \mathbf{m}$, i.e. the misfit of the inter-model constraints; for standard L2 norm, the time-lapse misfit reduces to $\chi_{TL} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N_{TL}} \cdot \sum_{i,j} \left(\frac{m_i - m_j}{\sigma_{TL_{i,j}}} \right)^2}$, where $\sigma_{TL_{i,j}}$ represents the standard deviation of the time-lapse constraint between the i^{th} and the j^{th} model parameters.
- $\Phi_P(\delta \mathbf{m}_P) = N_P \cdot \chi_P^2$ represents the measure of the prior misfit vector $\delta \mathbf{m}_P = \mathbf{m} - \mathbf{m}_P$, i.e. the difference between model vector \mathbf{m} and the prior model vector \mathbf{m}_P ; for standard L2 norm, the prior misfit reduces to $\chi_P = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N_P} \cdot \sum_{i=1}^{N_P} \left(\frac{m_i - m_{P_i}}{\sigma_{P_i}} \right)^2}$, where σ_{P_i} represents the standard deviation of the i^{th} prior constraint.

The objective function is minimized through an Iterative Reweighted Least Squared (IRLS) approach with Levenberg-Marquardt model update and the inversion process can be split in several inversion cycles: in each cycle it is possible to change the forward computation for each dataset (e.g. from 1D to 3D), as well as to insert/remove data/constraints from the objective function. Nevertheless, in each cycle the balance between data and model measures is not tuned with a Tikhonov method, but it is kept constant among iterations and governed only through the data and constraint standard deviations.

Data STDs

Data are always weighted through their standard deviations in the objective function and care shall be taken in the STDs definition. In EEMverter it is possible to re-calculate the data STDs (for instance when the instrument does not provide a reliable STD measure), summing two contribution up: a uniform relative standard deviation and a signal-dependent contribution. Furthermore, it is possible to increase the data STDs at the change of sign, for a significant improvement in the robustness of the inversion process. The .cfg settings for STD definition are (see the manual section on Configuration (.cfg) file for detailed explanations):

- For galvanic data, GalvanicNoiseLevel, GalvanicUniformStdDC, GalvanicUniformStdIP, GalvanicSumSquaredNoise, GalvanicFirstNegStd, GalvanicNCloseGates, GalvanicNCloseFactor, GalvanicCorrelatedNoise
- For inductive data, InductiveNoiseLevel, InductiveUniformStd, InductiveSumSquaredNoise, InductiveFirstNegStd, InductiveNCloseGates, InductiveNCloseFactor.

Typically, in full-decay IP inversion the number of IP data greatly surpasses the number of resistivity data, and a larger uniform STD helps in balancing IP and DC data in the objective function (IP uniform STD five/ten times greater than DC uniform STD is usually a good balance).

When running inversions of synthetic forward responses, it is possible to add noise to the data (AddNoise setting in .cfg file) not only when running the forward response (see section “How to run forward responses”), but also before running the inversion. In this way, it is possible to test different noise models without the need of re-computing the forward response.

All data STDs in EEMverter input files are indicated as relative uncertainty: nor zero-valued STDs nor zero-valued data are allowed.

Constraint values

Similarly to data STDs, the constraint values (roughness, time-lapse or prior constraint) in EEMverter are defined as relative uncertainties. For example, a vertical constraint equal to 1.0 means that a parameter variation between consecutive layers equal to 100% of the parameter value gives a misfit = 1.0 in the objective function (when the L2 norm is used for constraint definition).

The constraint values are the most important settings to tune in the inversion:

- Increasing/decreasing (e.g. doubling or halving) vertical and horizontal constraints will diminish/increase the importance of regularization in the inversion and retrieve rougher/smooth models;

- Increasing the ratio between vertical and horizontal constraint will favor layered models; decreasing the ratio will be more suitable for non-sedimentary environments and/or anomaly detection; typically, larger ratios between vertical and horizontal constraints are used with inductive data instead of galvanic data (for instance in the default configuration files distributed with EEMstudio).

The constraint settings are tuned in the .cfg file through the settings (see the manual section on Configuration (.cfg) file for detailed explanations):

- VertConstr, HorizConstrX, HorizConstrY for roughness constraints;
- ModelPriorValues, ModelPriorConstr for prior constraints.

Stopping criterion

The default stopping criterion in EEMverter (MisfitChange in .cfg/.EEM file) stops the iterative inversion in a cycle when none of these two conditions is met:

- the difference in the total misfit χ between consecutive iterations is larger than .cfg/.EEM setting RelNormChange
- the total misfit χ decreases and the difference in data misfit χ_d decreases more than .cfg/.EEM setting RelSubsetNormChange on a subset of the data larger than .cfg/.EEM setting SubsetNormChangeSize.

Another stopping criterion selectable in simplified inversion mode is DataMisfit, which stops the inversion when the data misfit χ_d goes below the .cfg threshold DataMisfitThreshold.

Starting model

The starting model is in importance the second tuning setting of an inversion. Two approaches are used by EEMverter for selecting a good starting (resistivity) model for the inversion:

- For galvanic data, the average apparent resistivity is used for resistivity starting model (UseAppRhoForInitialValue = 1 in .cfg file);
- For inductive data, an AutoStart inversion cycle is carried out, in which
 - Only one layer is used in the forward mesh
 - Tighter vertical/horizontal constraints are used for regularization (through setting SequentialAutoStartCScaling in simplified inversion mode)

No automatic approach is implemented in EEMverter for selecting good starting values for IP parameters:

- Low or High starting values for chargeability (i.e. φ_{max}/φ in MPA/CPA inversions or m_0 in RCC/CCC inversions) might give different inversion models, especially at depth close to the DOI
- In Cole-Cole inversions
 - Starting values for relaxation times τ outside the sensitivity range of measurements give bad results
 - Smaller τ starting values are preferred for inductive data
 - High starting values for C parameter give more sensitivity to τ and are preferred

Great care has been given in EEMverter in assuring equivalent starting models regardless of the ModelType selection in the inversion. Keywords can be used in the .cfg file (autoMPA, autoMIC, autoBIC, autoRCC, autoCCC, autoWHYCDF) for allowing EEMverter to compute automatically the equivalent starting value for any model type.

In the default .cfg files of EEMverter distributed with EEMstudio and in the default EEMverter settings, the autoMPA keyword is used for .cfg setting ModelTypeOfInitialValues. With these setting, the starting (and prior) values for parameters are defined in terms of the Maximum Phase Angle (MPA) re-parameterization of the Cole-Cole model, and the actual starting parameters of the inversion, which depend on the ModelType selection, are automatically computed by EEMverter. For instance, these two calls of EEMverter start from MPA and RCC equivalent parameters, which give the same initial misfit of the inversion:

- `.\EEMverterLITE_V7.10.exe GradM_IP.quo inv_2_2D.cfg MPA`, for running a Maximum Phase Angle (MPA) inversion.
- `.\EEMverterLITE_V7.10.exe GradM_IP.quo inv_2_2D.cfg RCC`, for running a Resistivity Cole-Cole (RCC) inversion.

Model discretization

In EEMverter, the model discretization is in importance the third tuning setting of an inversion. It is only the third because EEMverter defines adequate model discretization automatically, depending on the input data. Nevertheless, three main settings are often tuned in inversions: the number of layers, the minimum depth and the maximum depth (a user-defined selection of all model depths is also available through the .cfg setting ModelDefinedDepth). The default value for the number of layers (.cfg setting ModelNzNodes) is 21, which gives a good balance between vertical refinement and parameter sensitivity. In this regard, it is worth noting that no few-layer inversion mode, where model thicknesses enter the model space, is allowed in EEMverter.

The minimum and maximum depths of the model meshes can be set automatically in EEMverter (see AutoMeshSettings section in Configuration (.cfg) file description for details):

- For galvanic data, as a function of minimum and maximum pseudo-depth through the .cfg settings MinDepthFactor and MaxDepthFactor
- For inductive data, as a function of the transmitter size.

Especially for inductive data, the automatic min/max depth selection in EEMverter needs some tuning, because nor the model conductivity nor the system gates and signal level are taken into account in the depth selection:

- Use smaller min/max depths for very conductive environments;
- Use larger min/max depths for very resistive environments;
- Consider minimum/maximum acquisition times (in relation to the current waveform) for tuning first/last depths.

In EEMverter forward and model meshes are distinct, and the forward mesh discretization is automatically adapted to the model mesh definition. This adaptation is riskless for 1D (inductive) forward computations, but in 2D galvanic and 3D inductive computations choosing min/max depths and number of layers (very) different from the default values might affect forward accuracy. In particular, for galvanic computations it is better to choose a first layer thickness close to half of the minimum pseudo-depth. In this regard, pay attention when you use tables for defining the starting model in which the table dimension (dx, dy, MinDepth and MaxDepth) are explicitly defined.

Multi-cycle inversion

In EEMverter it is possible to define multiple inversion cycles for the inversion. Two main extra cycles are available in EEMverterLite:

- An AutoStart cycle, which retrieves the best starting model for inductive data (turned on by the .cfg setting SequentialAutoStart in simplified inversion mode)
- A sharp inversion cycle, which runs after the main inversion cycle and switches from L2 (or L1) model regularization to sharp regularization obtained through the Asymmetric Generalized Minimum Support (AGMS) norm (turned on by the .cfg setting SequentialSharp in simplified inversion mode).

In the sharp inversion cycle, the most important tuning setting in simplified inversion mode is the first of the SharpSettings (i.e. alpha), which controls the balance between data and model regularization in the objective function:

- Decrease (.e.g. halve) alpha for getting sharper inversion models (this might prevent a proper data fit);
- Increase (.e.g. double) alpha for allowing more model variability (this might cause a too-smooth final model).

Integral chargeability or full-decay galvanic IP inversion

A Time-Domain (TD) galvanic input file containing full-decay data can be inverted in three different modes, by selecting the data type for inversion: data type 2 for full-decay data modelling; data type 21 for integral chargeability data modelling; data type 22 for modeling only apparent resistivity values. The data type selection happens in three different places, depending on the input type used for EEMverter:

- by selecting the .cfg setting TDGalvDataType when running in simplified mode and using a single data file in the command arguments;
- by writing the proper data type in the .dls file when running in simplified mode with data list input;
- by writing the proper data type in the .EEM file when running in native mode.

In all cases, the forward modelling can be run with model types that consider IP, but:

- inversions with Cole-Cole like models require full-decay data, otherwise the spectral parameters cannot be resolved;
- inversions with IP modelling require IP data.

How to run forward responses

Forward responses in EEMverter can be handled both in native and simplified mode, with the latter being the usual approach. Two main options are provided, controlled by the number of iterations:

- Number of iterations = -1 -> synthetic modelling
- Number of iterations = 0 -> misfit computation

In both cases noise can be added to the data, through the .cfg setting AddNoise. When noise is added to the forward data, the extension of the output files is changed in:

- .tip (WriteAddedNoise=0) or .tap (WriteAddedNoise=1, added noise contained in the file) for time-domain galvanic data;
- .lil (WriteAddedNoise=0) or .tin (WriteAddedNoise=1, added noise contained in the file) for time-domain inductive data.

Forward responses for synthetic modelling

When the number of iterations is set to -1, either in the .cfg file in simplified mode (setting CycleNIte) or in the .EEM file for native mode (setting #Ite in section %13), a forward response is carried out, with the following characteristics:

- when the standard deviations STDs are re-computed by EEMverter (RecomputeGalvanicSTDs > 0 and/or RecomputeInductiveSTDs > 0), the forward signal, which depends on the model, is used for the STDs computation;
- the data misfit is computed using the forward STDs and not the data STDs (this makes a difference only in linear data space);
- the DOI is computed using the forward STDs, without considering data misfit (when DOI computation is turned on in the .cfg/.EEM file).

For forward computations with non-uniform models, the standard procedure is to call EEMverter in simplified mode using a table for defining the model. This can be done in two ways: defining in the .cfg file “ModelTypeOfInitialValues = external” and indicating the name of the table file as command argument, or assigning directly the name of the table file to ModelTypeOfInitialValues.

For a given table file defined in terms of Cole-Cole parameters (or any re-parameterization of Cole-Cole model), it is possible to run forward responses in resistivity or with CPA-like models without modifications to the table. Indeed, the model type of the forward response is indicated in the .cfg setting “ModelType”, which can indicate the model type itself or the “external” keyword,

Using “external” in the .cfg table for both “ModelType” and “ModelTypeOfInitialValues” settings, call examples for EEMverter look like:

- `.\EEMverterLITE_V7.10.exe tTEM.ely fwr_2_2D.cfg MPA TwoBlocks.txt`, for running a Maximum Phase Angle (MPA) forward model. In `TwoBlocks.txt` the model is defined in terms of MPA parameters (ModelType=14), so EEMverter takes the parameter values of the table as written in the file.

- `.\EEMverterLITE_V7.10.exe tTEM.ely fwr_2_2D.cfg RCC TwoBlocks.txt`, for running a Resistivity Cole-Cole (RCC) forward model. In `TwoBlocks.txt` the model is defined in terms of MPA parameters (ModelType=14), so EEMverter transforms the MPA parameters to the equivalent RCC ones and then runs the forward response. Considering that the MPA and RCC parameters are equivalent, the corresponding complex resistivity is identical in the two modelling, and the forward responses do not differ.
- `.\EEMverterLITE_V7.10.exe tTEM.ely fwr_2_2D.cfg CPA TwoBlocks.txt`, for running a CPA forward model. In `TwoBlocks.txt` the model is defined in terms of MPA parameters (ModelType=14), so EEMverter takes the first two parameters (resistivity and phase) for the modelling.
- `.\EEMverterLITE_V7.10.exe tTEM.ely fwr_2_2D.cfg CPA TwoBlocks_RCC.txt`, for running a CPA forward model. In `TwoBlocks_RCC.txt` the model is defined in terms of Resistivity Cole-Cole (RCC) parameters (ModelType=11), so EEMverter transforms the RCC parameters to MPA and takes the first two parameters (resistivity and phase) for the modelling.

In all cases, it is recommended to set only one cycle in the `.cfg` file for forward computation, e.g. turning off AutoStart and SequentialSharp cycles.

In the table definition, both for simplified (extension `.txt`) and advanced (extension `.tbl`) formats, two main options are available for defining the table dimension:

- Explicit definition of horizontal spacings `dx` and `dy`, as well as minimum and maximum depths `MinDepth` and `MaxDepth` of the model. In this case, the table settings are copied to the `.cfg` settings defining the model mesh, i.e.:
 - `.cfg` setting `ModelMinDepth` = table setting `MinDepth`
 - `.cfg` setting `ModelMaxDepth` = table setting `MaxDepth`
 - `.cfg` setting `ModelXNodeSpacing` = table setting `dx`
 - `.cfg` setting `ModelYNodeSpacing` = table setting `dy`
 - `.cfg` setting `ModelNzNodes` = table setting `Nz`

If the horizontal table extension (`Nx` and `Ny`) is smaller than the model mesh extension, the table is automatically continued in the `x-y` directions with the closest model columns.

- No definition of table dimension (optional info `dx`, `dy`, `MinDepth` and `MaxDepth` not defined). In this case, the model mesh dimension (`ModelMinDepth`, `ModelMaxDepth`, `ModelXNodeSpacing`, `ModelYNodeSpacing` and `ModelNzNodes`) is independent of the table size (`Nx`, `Ny`, `Nz`), i.e.:
 - if the table extension (`Nx`, `Ny` and `Nz`) is smaller than the model mesh extension, the table is automatically continued in the `x-y-z` directions with the closest model columns/row;
 - layer thicknesses and horizontal distances among nodes depends on the `.cfg` settings, and with automatic computation of `ModelMinDepth`, `ModelMaxDepth`, `ModelXNodeSpacing`, `ModelYNodeSpacing` the same table will generate models with different sizes depending on the data file.

With both options for table definition, it is possible to indicate with an external file user-defined depths for the model mesh, through the `ModelDefinedDepth` `.cfg` setting. The `ModelDefinedDepth` `.cfg` setting prevails on the `MinDepth/MaxDepth` table settings and on the `ModelMinDepth/ ModelMaxDepth` `.cfg` settings.

Forward responses for misfit computation

When the number of iterations is set to 0, either in the .cfg file in simplified mode (setting CycleNlte) or in the .EEM file for native mode (setting #lte in section %13), a forward response is carried out, with the following characteristics:

- when the standard deviations STDs are re-computed by EEMverter (RecomputeGalvanicSTDs > 0 and/or RecomputeInductiveSTDs > 0), the STDs computation depends on the signal level and change of sign (and not on the forward response level/change of sign);
- the data misfit is computed using the data STDs;
- the DOI is computed using the data STDs, considering data misfit (when DOI computation is turned on in the .cfg/.EEM file): the uncertainty used on DOI computation is the larger between data STD and data misfit.

How to run Time-lapse and Cross-mesh inversions

Similarly to standard inversions, Time-lapse (TL) inversions can be handled both in native mode, through the .EEM file, and in simplified mode, through the use of a data file list (file extension .dls).

Actually, these implementations allow for:

- Time-Lapse inversions, among different datasets acquired at different times but with coincident electrodes/Tx-Rx positions
- Time-Lapse inversions, among different datasets acquired at different times but with different electrodes/Tx-Rx positions
- Inversions of different datasets acquired at the same time, with different electrodes/Tx-Rx positions, in which we want to constraints models (actually, model meshes) that are close in space (for instance, 2D profiles where they cross)

Therefore, the variables of the .cfg file that refer to TL inversions are actually named “TLX” variables, because they handle both Time-Lapse and Cross-Mesh inversions/constraints.

In both native and simplified mode, the constraint mesh generation between different meshes can be handled automatically through the .cfg file. In this case, the possible different position of the meshes linked to different data files is handled through the .cfg settings “MaxTLXDistance” and “RefTLXDistance”:

- Constraints are built among nodes of meshes linked to different data files only when the horizontal distance between nodes is lower than/equal to MaxTLXDistance
- When the distance is greater than RefTLXDistance , the constraint STD is called with distance as $STD=input\ STD*Dist/RefDist$

TLX inversions in native mode

For TLX galvanic inversions the .EEM file should indicate:

- Minimum two data files
- A distinct model for each data file
- A model mesh for each model
- Constraints among different model meshes
 - For defining the TLX constraint mesh through a .cfg file, it is necessary to indicate in the .cfg settings:
 - RoughnessORTimeLapse=1
 - The value for TLXReferenceModelMeshID (the constraints are among the model mesh indicated in the EEM file and the model mesh indicated in the .cfg file through TLXReferenceModelMeshID)
- Preferably, a different norm for each data set
- Preferably, a different norm for the TLX constraints

For using the Asymmetric Generalised Minimum Support norm as TLX norm, use the following settings in the .EEM file:

- NormType 5
- NormName generalizedminimumsupport
- NormSettings 0.50E+00 1.35E+00 2.00E+00 !alpha, p1, p2

“Normal” L1/L2 norms are instead identified by:

- NormType 1
 - NormName L2
 - NormSettings none
-
- NormType 2
 - NormName L1
 - NormSettings none

The standard deviation of the TLX constraints is indicated in the .cfg file (or in the vtk file, when vtk file are used instead of cfg file for defining the constraints).

TLX inversions in simplified mode

In simplified mode, the TLX inversion runs with the use of the data list file with extension .dls. This file contains, in each row, the data file name, the data type, the clipping area ID and the model ID. An optional header line is allowed, as long as the first character is the percentage symbol "%". For example, a .dls file for resistivity Time-Lapse or Cross-Mesh inversion looks like:

% FileName	DataType	ClipAreaID	ModelID
File1.qui	22	0	1
File2.qui	22	0	2
File3.qui	22	0	3

In simplified mode, the norm type and settings of the TLX constraints can be selected in the .cfg file through the settings TLXNormType, NTLXSettings & TLXSettings, while the reference model ID through ReferenceTLX. With more than two data files in the .dls input, ReferenceTLX=-1 allows for constraining each model with the previous.

Call example:

- `.\EEMverterLITE_V7.10.exe DipDipM_plume0-1-2.dls inv_2_2D.cfg`
Using an explicit configuration file

In simplified mode, distinct .cfg files are generated by EEMverter, together with the .EEM file, for all model meshes linked to the data files and for the TLX constraint meshes, such that distinct NormIDs are used for constraints related to different models.

Demo files

DCIP

In this folder 3 field datasets and 3 synthetic sequences are proposed. All field data sequences are acquired with the Gradient array and 100% duty cycle time-domain IP, with the Terrameter LS2 (ABEM) instrument in full-waveform acquisition. The synthetic sequences are with 81 electrodes (gradient array) and 41 electrodes (gradient and dipole-dipole arrays), with and without IP. Some of the files are accompanied by inversions and/or forward models.

Field

- ArnOLD.qui, gradient array, 10 m spacing, 100% duty cycle, max decay length 12.3 s, without processing. Sedimentary environment, weak IP.
- ArnOLD_Proc.qui, gradient array, 10 m spacing, 100% duty cycle, max decay length 12.3 s, with processing. Corresponding inversions:
 - ArnOLD_Proc_inv_2_2D_RES, resistivity-only inversion;
 - ArnOLD_Proc_inv_2_2D_CPA, Constant Phase Angle (CPA) full-decay inversion.
- Bubbiano.qui, gradient array, 10 m spacing, 100% duty cycle, max decay length 7.5 s, without processing. Sedimentary environment, presence of conglomerates, mild IP.
- Bubbiano_Proc.qui, gradient array, 10 m spacing, 100% duty cycle, max decay length 7.5 s, with processing. Corresponding inversions:
 - Bubbiano_Proc_inv_2_2D_RES, resistivity-only inversion.
- Madesimo.qui, gradient array, 10 m spacing, 100% duty cycle, max decay length 6.3 s, without processing. Mountain environment, significant IP.
- Madesimo_Proc.qui, gradient array, 10 m spacing, 100% duty cycle, max decay length 6.3 s, with processing.

Synthetic

- DipDipM_IP.quo, dipole-dipole array, 41 electrodes, 100% duty cycle, 12.3 s decay length. Created with synthetic model TwoBlocks.txt and Maximum Phase Angle (MPA) modelling. Corresponding forward/inversion folders:
 - DipDipM_IP_fwr_2_2D_MPA, forward folder
- GradM_IP.quo, gradient array, 41 electrodes, 100% duty cycle, 12.3 s decay length. Created with synthetic model TwoBlocks.txt and Maximum Phase Angle (MPA) modelling. Corresponding forward/inversion folders:
 - GradM_IP_fwr_2_2D_MPA, forward folder
- DipDipM_IP_noise.tap, dipole-dipole array, 41 electrodes, 100% duty cycle, 12.3 s decay length. Created with synthetic model TwoBlocks.txt and Maximum Phase Angle (MPA) modelling. Noise added to the data and explicitly written in the file. Corresponding forward/inversion folders:
 - DipDipM_IP_fwr_2_2D_add_noise_MPA, forward folder
- GradM_IP_noise.tap, gradient array, 41 electrodes, 100% duty cycle, 12.3 s decay length. Created with synthetic model TwoBlocks.txt and Maximum Phase Angle (MPA) modelling. Noise added to the data and explicitly written in the file. Corresponding forward/inversion folders:
 - GradM_IP_fwr_2_2D_add_noise_MPA, forward folder

- GradM_IP_noise_inv_2_2D_RES, resistivity-only inversion
- GradM_IP_noise_inv_2_2D_CPA, CPA full-decay inversion. The CPA modelling does not describe properly the decay shapes, because the forward data were generated with MPA modelling.
- GradM_IP_noise_inv_2_2D_CPA_IntIP, CPA integral-chargeability inversion. The integral-chargeability inversion fits the MPA forward data, but with quite misleading chargeability values. This is because slow-decaying mild IP signals give strong integral-chargeability anomalies.
- GradM_IP_noise_inv_2_2D_MPA, MPA full-decay inversion. This simulation shows a good fit and a good model (as expected).
- GradXL_IP.quo, gradient array, 81 electrodes, 100% duty cycle, 12.3 s decay length. Created with Maximum Phase Angle (MPA) modelling.
- Time-lapse modelling:
 - DipDipM_Plume0.quo, dipole-dipole array, 41 electrodes, resistivity-only modelling. Created with synthetic model plume0.txt.
 - DipDipM_Plume1.quo, dipole-dipole array, 41 electrodes, resistivity-only modelling. Created with synthetic model plume0.txt.
 - DipDipM_Plume2.quo, dipole-dipole array, 41 electrodes, resistivity-only modelling. Created with synthetic model plume0.txt.
 - Corresponding inversion folder:
 - DipDipM_plume0_1_2_inv_2_2D_TL_RES

TEM

Two field examples and three synthetic sequences are proposed. The field examples are data acquired in the same site (Bubbiano, where one of the field galvanic dataset was acquired as well), with Loupe instrument (Loupe Geophysics) and tTEM instrument (TEMcompany). The synthetic data are generated with three systems (Loupe, tTEM and Tem2Go), both with 1D forward modelling and 2D forward modelling.

Field

- Bubbiano_Loupe_375Hz.emy, Loupe acquisition with 375 Hz acquisition rate, x, y and z components. Raw data converted from the instrument .dat file. No processing.
- Bubbiano_Loupe_375Hz_Avg.emy, Loupe acquisition with 375 Hz acquisition rate, x, y and z components. Averaged data every 2.5 meters. No processing.
- Bubbiano_Loupe_375Hz_Proc_Avg.emy, Loupe acquisition with 375 Hz acquisition rate, x, y and z components. Averaged data every 2.5 meters. Data processed. Corresponding inversion folder:
 - Bubbiano_Loupe_375Hz_Proc_Avg_inv_2_1D_RES, 2D model mesh and 1D forward response, XZ inversion.
- tTEM_Bubbiano.emy, tTEM acquisition, low moment and high moment, No processing.
- tTEM_Bubbiano_Proc.emy, tTEM acquisition, low moment and high moment. Data processed. Corresponding inversion folder:
 - tTEM_Bubbiano_Proc_inv_2_1D_RES, 2D model mesh and 1D forward response inversion.

Synthetic

- Loupe.ely, 41 soundings. Created with synthetic model TwoBlocks.txt and resistivity-only modelling, 1D forward response. Corresponding forward folder:
 - Loupe_fwr_2_1D_RES, forward folder
- tTEM.ely, 41 soundings. Created with synthetic model TwoBlocks.txt and resistivity-only modelling, 1D forward response. Corresponding forward folder:
 - tTEM_fwr_2_1D_RES, forward folder
- Tem2Go.ely, 41 soundings. Created with synthetic model TwoBlocks.txt and resistivity-only modelling, 1D forward response. Corresponding forward folder:
 - Tem2Go_fwr_2_1D_RES, forward folder
- Loupe_2D.ely, 41 soundings. Created with synthetic model TwoBlocks.txt and resistivity-only modelling, 2D forward response. Corresponding inversion folder:
 - Loupe_2D_inv_2_1D_RES, inversion folder with 2D model and 1D forward response. The pantleg effect is clearly visible in the data.
- tTEM_2D.ely, 41 soundings. Created with synthetic model TwoBlocks.txt and resistivity-only modelling, 2D forward response. Corresponding inversion folder:
 - tTEM_2D_inv_2_1D_RES, inversion folder with 2D model and 1D forward response. The pantleg effect is clearly visible in the data.
- Tem2Go_2D.ely, 41 soundings. Created with synthetic model TwoBlocks.txt and resistivity-only modelling, 2D forward response. Corresponding inversion folder:
 - Tem2Go_2D_inv_2_1D_RES, inversion folder with 2D model and 1D forward response. The pantleg effect is clearly visible in the data.